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Article

Impact of Leader Behavior on Employee Experience and Job Satisfaction in Educational Institutions

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Abstract: Given the relevance of leadership in the educational environment, there is a need to identify the key elements that influence teacher well-being. Therefore, the present study addresses the impact of leader behavior, specifically initial structure and consideration, on employee experience and job satisfaction in Peruvian educational institutions. The research included a sample of 651 regular basic education teachers in Peru and used a structural equation model using PLS-SEM to evaluate the hypotheses. The following were measured: three dimensions of the employee experience: sensorial, intellectual, and emotional, using validated and reliable instruments. The results indicated that the initial structure positively impacts the three dimensions of the employee experience, while consideration significantly influences the sensorial and emotional experiences but not the intellectual ones. Likewise, it was proven that the three dimensions of the employee experience positively impact job satisfaction. It is concluded that effective leadership, which combines structural clarity and emotional support, improves the work environment and increases staff satisfaction. Finally, implementing leadership training programs is suggested to strengthen these competencies in educational leaders.

Keywords: educational leadership; job satisfaction; employee experience; leader behavior

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1. Introduction

Leadership plays a crucial role in shaping the work environment and employees' perceptions of their overall job experience and satisfaction in educational institutions (Jiménez-Bucarey et al., 2021). Despite extensive research on leadership and job satisfaction, it remains critical to understand how specific aspects of leader behavior, such as initial framing and consideration, influence the overall employee experience and, ultimately, job satisfaction (García-Salirrosas et al., 2023). Researchers are currently focused on unraveling these links to provide a clear and practical framework for improving leadership management in the educational context.

A significant challenge lies in identifying and understanding the elements of leader behavior that impact the sensory, intellectual, and emotional experience of employees and how these experiences affect their job satisfaction (González-Díaz et al., 2021). In a context where educational institutions face challenges related to staff retention, educational quality,

and employee well-being, empirical evidence is necessary to improve leadership practices, organizational climate, and institutional effectiveness.

In Latin America, the educational sector faces critical challenges in leadership management and employee job satisfaction. The UNESCO International Institute for Higher Education in Latin America and the Caribbean (IESALC, 2024) highlighted these issues during the Regional Conference on Higher Education (CRES+5), held in Brasilia from 13–15 March 2024. Structural and socioeconomic factors have impacted educational quality, creating an adverse environment characterized by high workloads, lack of recognition, and poor working conditions. The main problem is that many educational leaders do not have adequate training to handle the complexities of the academic environment, resulting in ineffective leadership practices (Cohen de Lara et al., 2024).

This situation is further exacerbated by the lack of resources and institutional support, leaving leaders without the necessary tools to foster a positive work environment (Macfarlane et al., 2024). Consequently, employees experience low levels of job satisfaction, which negatively impact education quality and staff retention. Ineffective leadership in the region contributes to an adverse organizational climate characterized by high staff turnover, stress, and demotivation (Ghamrawi et al., 2024).

A major problem is the lack of effective leadership in educational institutions. While numerous studies identify leadership as a key factor in improving educational quality, leadership training programs for school administrators in the region have not generated significant impacts on their practices. The authors argue that, despite training initiatives, these programs often lack evaluation and follow-up, which limits their effectiveness in improving teacher performance and organizational climate (Weinstein et al., 2018).

The Peruvian context presents even greater challenges. Teachers face high workloads, have limited access to professional development programs, and there are scarce recognition opportunities, all of which negatively affect job satisfaction and retention in the education system. Moreover, the absence of organizational strategies to enhance employee experience has led to high levels of dissatisfaction and teacher turnover (Laura-Arias et al., 2024). The urgent need to improve teachers' work experience stems from the growing demand for quality education in the country.

Recent research highlights the importance of servant leadership as an effective strategy to enhance job satisfaction and the perception of organizational justice among Peruvian teachers (Agustin-Silvestre et al., 2024). In this regard, leadership centered on support and structural clarity has been shown to positively impact teachers' work experience, reinforcing the need for further exploration of these effects within Peru's education system. Moreover, the validation of a scale to measure employee experience in the education sector has identified three key dimensions: sensory, intellectual, and emotional. Therefore, understanding how educational leadership influences these dimensions is essential for developing strategies that strengthen the school environment and improve teacher retention (Acuña-Hurtado et al., 2024).

Despite efforts to professionalize school leadership in Peru, the lack of induction programs and limited access to continuous training hinder the implementation of effective strategies for teacher satisfaction and well-being. The absence of a comprehensive approach to leadership training remains a significant barrier, underscoring the need for rigorous and context-specific research regarding the impact of leadership on teacher experience and job satisfaction.

This study seeks to provide empirical evidence on the influence of educational leadership on teachers' experience and job satisfaction in Peruvian institutions. By analyzing leader behavior in terms of initial structure and consideration, the research aims to generate insights for policy development and leadership strengthening in educational institutions,

ultimately contributing to a better organizational climate and enhanced educational quality in the country.

Additionally, improving employees' work experience in the education sector is urgent in the Peruvian context due to the increasing demand for quality education (Laura-Arias et al., 2024). The problem manifests itself in leaders' inadequate consideration of employees' emotional, intellectual, and sensory needs (Gómez-Bayona et al., 2024). This deficiency in attention and support negatively impacts job satisfaction and educational performance (Romero-Lora et al., 2024). Despite efforts to implement educational reforms, the lack of a comprehensive approach to training and developing educational leaders remains a significant obstacle. Educational institutions in Peru must invest in leadership training to promote a healthy and productive work environment, improving employee experience and satisfaction (Prialé et al., 2024).

The primary objective of this research is to analyze the impact of leader behavior, specifically initial structure and consideration, on employee experience (sensory, intellectual, and emotional) and job satisfaction in educational institutions. This analysis will identify key factors contributing to a fulfilling work experience and higher job satisfaction, providing a solid foundation for developing effective leadership strategies (Espinoza et al., 2024).

This research offers valuable insights for implementing leadership practices that foster a positive work environment (Arviv Elyashiv & Hanuka, 2024). By improving both employee experience and job satisfaction, the findings can significantly contribute to developing management policies and strategies in the education sector (Liu, 2024). Ultimately, this could enhance employee well-being and performance, strengthening educational quality and institution staff retention.

This study is structured into six sections: Section 2 presents the literature review, Section 3 details the materials and methods used, Section 4 presents the obtained results, Section 5 develops the analysis and discussion of the findings, and finally, Section 6 outlines the conclusions of the research.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Leader Behavior and Job Satisfaction

The concept of Initial Structure (IS) was proposed in leadership studies, particularly within the behavioral approach developed by Ohio State University (Halpin, 1955). The author defines this variable as the behaviors leaders exhibit to outline their relationships with subordinates' functioning clearly. It is intended to establish a structure with a mechanism that allows the group members to interact with each other and the leader to solve potential problems that may arise without needing to depend on the leader to request specific instructions. Over the years, scientific research has demonstrated the influence of the initial structure on job satisfaction and performance (Judge et al., 2004) and on job satisfaction and performance (Rowold et al., 2014). For their part, (Lambert et al., 2012) point out that insufficient levels, but also excessive levels of initial structure, generate unfavorable attitudes in employees and that the balance between insufficient and excessive levels is mediated by trust in leaders. It is important to consider the initial structure in the behavior of leaders because employees perceive this and influence their citizenship behavior in the organization, which eventually impacts well-being and job satisfaction (Liang et al., 2023). From the above development, the following is concluded.

Like the initial structure construct, the consideration construct (CO) was also proposed by Halpin (1955). In this case, the leader's behavior demonstrates friendship, mutual trust, respect, and warmth in the relationship with his subordinates. It is about the human side of interpersonal relationships. In this case, previous studies confirm the positive relationship between individualized consideration and job satisfaction (Chen et al., 2005).

In the educational sector, [Balyer and Oezcan \(2012\)](#) confirmed teachers' positive perceptions when principals show leadership skills that highlight individualized consideration. On the contrary, when the perception of leadership is negative, that is, signs of negligent behavior and/or carelessness are shown, the levels of perception of individualized consideration are significantly reduced ([Snell et al., 2013](#)). From the above, it can be deduced that

H1a: *The initial structure (ST) positively and directly impacts job satisfaction (JS).*

H1b: *Consideration (CO) positively and directly impacts job satisfaction (JS).*

2.2. The Initial Structure and the Employee Experience

According to [Walumbwa et al. \(2019\)](#), research showing the positive effects of leadership focusing on the "initial structure" is numerous and diverse. They pointed out that leadership focused on the "initial structure" increases employee performance and reduces job turnover due to efforts to manage a good quality work environment. That is why the focus on the "initial structure" positively influences motivation and work commitment ([Bock et al., 2008](#)).

Another positive effect of the "initial structure" dimension is the perception of justice in the work environment. Leadership focusing on "initial structure" at moderate levels has a significant positive effect on the perception of justice management in the organization, which positively impacts the work environment ([Tremblay et al., 2018](#)). On the other hand, the positive effect of this leadership approach on knowledge management in organizations has also been documented. According to [Huang et al. \(2008\)](#), leadership focused on the "initial structure" significantly and positively affects employees' intention to share their knowledge with other employees. In this same sense, previous studies demonstrate the positive relationship that leadership focused on the "initial structure" has on employee creativity through the increase in the perception of trust in the organization and the sense of ownership that employees have of their organizations ([Jo et al., 2015](#)). The above is in line with research that proves the positive effect that leadership focused on the "initial structure" has on perceived organizational support ([Gaudet & Tremblay, 2017](#)). The literature review allows us to conclude that

H2a: *The initial structure (IS) positively and directly impacts the employee's sensory experience (SE).*

H2b: *Initial structure (IS) positively and directly impacts employee intellectual experience (IE).*

H2c: *Initial structure (IS) positively and directly impacts employee emotional experience (EE).*

2.3. Employee Consideration and Experience

The leader's behavior towards his subordinates can positively or negatively influence his results within the organization and his experience in it ([Jauregui-Arroyo et al., 2023](#)). [Alcázar Cruz \(2020\)](#) indicated that the leader's consideration, reflected in his concern for subordinates and their professional development, among other aspects, favorably impacts the employees' perception of the company, generating motivation and commitment. Likewise, the leader must consider the sensory stimuli the organization offers through the physical space where the work is carried out ([Moldes Farelo & Gómez, 2021](#)). This is because the workplace serves as the setting for employees' sensory experiences, so leaders must create environments where employees feel valued and committed as part of the company ([Gavilan et al., 2013](#)). To achieve this positive sensory experience, the physical,

technological, contractual, productive, and professional environments must be considered (Donawa Torres, 2018).

The educational field is a sector in which professionals experience mixed feelings since, although they feel satisfaction with the work they do, they also face constant challenges in the educational context (Vicente Coronado et al., 2019). Therefore, the leader must pay special attention to the individual needs of the collaborators (Jauregui-Arroyo et al., 2023). Among these needs, it is crucial to consider the intellectual experience, which refers to the values and the impact that the approach, knowledge, and internalization have on the employee (Moldes Farelo & Gómez, 2021). The authors Vicente Coronado et al. (2019) and Gavilan et al. (2013) emphasized that leaders must focus on this intellectual experience so that employees feel motivated and committed to the organization and achieve superior performance. In this sense, there is a significant influence between the leader's consideration and the intellectual experience of employees (Alcázar Cruz, 2020).

Previous investigations have shown that the leader's behavior affects his employees, especially in the emotional experience, which refers to the enjoyment of work and is closely linked to the experiences of job performance (Moldes Farelo & Gómez, 2021). Therefore, the attention that the leader pays to this emotional experience will make employees feel more motivated in their activities, which will result in greater productivity (Gavilan et al., 2013). Hurtado Palomino et al. (2021) emphasized that in the evolving landscape of the educational sector, leaders must prioritize differentiating factors that enhance the emotional experiences of their team members. This focus is essential for organizations to gain a competitive advantage. For this consideration to have a positive impact on the emotional experience, it is necessary to consider factors such as interpersonal relationships, feedback, positive satisfaction, stability, organizational support, and recognition (Barrué & Sánchez-Gómez, 2021).

H3a: *Consideration (CO) positively and directly impacts employee sensory experience (SE).*

H3b: *Consideration (CO) positively and directly impacts employee intellectual experience (IE).*

H3c: *Consideration (CO) positively and directly impacts employee emotional experience (EE).*

2.4. Employee Experience and Job Satisfaction

Previous studies examine the factors that affect job satisfaction, including the experience in the work environment (Gavilan et al., 2013). Job satisfaction is fundamental to the development and success of any organization since working conditions positively influence employee well-being (Diaz Dumont et al., 2023). In this context, the sensory experience, characterized by the stimuli of the work environment, must include all the elements that promote employee satisfaction (Hurtado Palomino et al., 2021). In addition, De Los Heros Rondenil et al. (2020) emphasized that working conditions and the environment are essential factors that favorably affect job satisfaction and that decision-makers must consider them when planning.

Intellectual experience (IE) refers to the employee's understanding of the organizational culture, values, and meaning; therefore, its impact on employee satisfaction is considerable (Hurtado Palomino et al., 2021). Furthermore, it is important to highlight that the consideration of the intellectual experience in organizations is gaining relevance since as it is directly related to employee knowledge, it promotes the development of competencies to learn and generate knowledge, which, in turn, positively affects job satisfaction and social development within the company (Durán, 2019). Therefore, De Los Heros Rondenil et al. (2020) pointed out that to evaluate job satisfaction, it is essential to gradually acquire

knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and behaviors to propose strategies that optimize employee satisfaction.

The common aspects in various definitions found in the literature suggest that job satisfaction encompasses a set of attitudes and feelings of the individual towards his or her job (De Los Heros Rondenil et al., 2020). This satisfaction is linked to the emotional experience, which refers to the pleasure derived from work, that is, to the experiences and performance in work tasks (Hurtado Palomino et al., 2021). Therefore, the analysis of both variables is crucial since it reflects the degree to which an employee finds his or her work gratifying based on his or her response to the emotional experience (De Los Heros Rondenil et al., 2020). Likewise, it is essential to highlight that recognition, achievements, promotion, and the very nature of the work are elements that must be cultivated within the emotional experience so that the employee feels stimulated and, in this way, achieves better performance within the organization (Diaz Dumont et al., 2023).

H4a: *Employee sensory experience (SE) positively and directly impacts job satisfaction (JS).*

H4b: *Employee intellectual experience (IE) positively and directly impacts job satisfaction (JS).*

H4c: *Employee emotional experience (EE) positively and directly impacts job satisfaction (JS).*

Finally, Figure 1 presents a graphical representation of the theoretical model used in this study.

Figure 1. Theoretical model.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Sample and Procedure

This study involved 651 teachers of regular basic education belonging to the preschool, primary, and secondary levels of a private educational network in Peru. Data were collected using non-probabilistic convenience sampling (Otzen & Manterola, 2017). The inclusion criteria for participants established that they had to be classroom teachers without administrative functions and had worked in the educational network during the year 2023. This study had the approval of the ethics committee of the Graduate School of a private university in Peru (2024-CE-EPG-00027) and the authorization of the administrators of each educational institution that was part of the network. The survey was implemented virtually using Google Forms and was distributed through WhatsApp by the directors of the participating institutions.

At the beginning of the survey, instructions were included informing participants that their collaboration would be voluntary, guaranteeing the anonymity of the responses. Teachers were required to give their informed consent to continue, in compliance with the ethical principles established for research with human beings according to the Declaration of Helsinki (Manzini, 2000; Puri et al., 2009). Data collection took place between January

and May 2024. Table 1 below presents the descriptive sociodemographic data of the study participants.

Table 1. Sociodemographic data.

Category		Frequency	Percentage
Age range	18–30	100	15.4
	31–40	200	30.7
	41–50	234	35.9
	51–60	101	15.5
	61–70	16	2.5
Gender	Male	239	36.7
	Female	412	63.3
Educational level	Bachelor	292	44.9
	Doctor	3	0.5
	Institute/Pedagogical	200	30.7
	Master	156	24.0

3.2. Instrument

To evaluate the employee experience variable, the questionnaire was developed by (Gavilan et al., 2013), and validated for the educational sector in the Peruvian context (Acuña-Hurtado et al., 2024). This instrument evaluates employee experience through three dimensions: sensory experience (SE) with four items, intellectual experience (IE) with seven items, and emotional experience (EE) with three items, totaling 14 items. To assess the leader behavior variable, we utilized a scale that comprises two dimensions: Initiating Structure (IS) and Consideration (CO). Each dimension includes 10 items, resulting in a total of 20 items. To evaluate job satisfaction, we employed a questionnaire consisting of a unidimensional construct with nine items. The items in both scales were rated using a 5-point Likert scale, where one indicates “totally disagree” and five signifies “totally agree”.

It is important to note that the questionnaire was validated by four experts from the education sector, who confirmed the adequacy and clarity of the questions’ formulation. Additionally, a pilot test was carried out with 40 participants, which made it possible to verify that all the questions were understood in the sense in which they were posed. This validation was supported by a Cronbach’s Alpha reliability coefficient greater than 0.80 in all constructs.

3.3. Data Analysis Procedure

Two types of statistical software were used for data analysis: (1) IBM SPSS version 25, used to perform the descriptive analysis of the participants’ sociodemographic variables, and (2) Smart-PLS version 4.0, used to evaluate the reliability of the instrument, as well as the convergent and discriminant validity. In addition, this last software was used to test the hypotheses of the structural model using the partial least squares method (PLS-SEM).

PLS-SEM is a comprehensive multivariate statistical approach incorporating structural and measurement components, allowing for the simultaneous examination of relationships between multiple variables within a conceptual model. It is distinguished by its ability to manage multiple variables, typically three or more. The present study employed PLS-SEM due to its suitability for facilitating theory building and validation, allowing for a deeper understanding of the phenomena investigated (J. F. Hair et al., 2019). The significance of the path coefficients was determined using the *p* and *t* values to evaluate the structural model. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was also used to indicate the model’s predictive capacity. Finally, the model’s overall fit was verified using the root mean square of the residuals (SRMR).

4. Results

4.1. Measurement Model Evaluation

J. F. Hair et al. (2019) state that evaluating the measurement model requires confirming convergent and discriminant validity. Convergent validity is verified by ensuring that the factor loadings of all items are equal to or greater than 0.7. Likewise, Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (CR) must be evaluated, whose values must be equal to or greater than 0.70. In addition, it is necessary to calculate the average variance extracted (AVE), which must be greater than 0.50. In this study, Cronbach's alpha values were between 0.951 and 0.980, exceeding the minimum recommended threshold of 0.7 (J. Hair et al., 2017). Similarly, the composite reliability (CR) showed values between 0.953 and 0.980, also above the reference value of 0.7 (Kline, 2015). Additionally, the AVE values ranged between 0.787 and 0.910, exceeding the threshold of 0.5. These results demonstrate that convergent validity is adequately met for all constructs in the measurement model (Table 2).

Table 2. Validation of the measurement model (reliability and convergent validity).

Construct	Item	Loading	Alpha	CR	AVE
Consideration (CO)	CO1	0.872	0.969	0.970	0.802
	CO2	0.908			
	CO3	0.878			
	CO5	0.881			
	CO6	0.883			
	CO7	0.917			
	CO8	0.918			
	CO9	0.885			
	CO10	0.915			
	Emotional experience (EE)	EE1			
EE2		0.945			
EE3		0.971			
Intellectual experience (IE)	IE1	0.921	0.980	0.980	0.891
	IE2	0.949			
	IE3	0.944			
	IE4	0.950			
	IE5	0.953			
	IE6	0.936			
	IE7	0.953			
Initiating structure (IS)	IS1	0.916	0.980	0.980	0.849
	IS2	0.923			
	IS3	0.914			
	IS4	0.929			
	IS5	0.929			
	IS6	0.915			
	IS7	0.936			
	IS8	0.912			
	IS9	0.943			
	IS10	0.896			

Table 2. *Cont.*

Construct	Item	Loading	Alpha	CR	AVE
Job Satisfaction (JS)	JS1	0.900	0.961	0.963	0.787
	JS2	0.905			
	JS3	0.892			
	JS4	0.857			
	JS5	0.930			
	JS6	0.903			
	JS7	0.881			
	JS9	0.825			
	Sensory experience (SE)	SE1			
SE2		0.953			
SE3		0.958			
SE4		0.922			

Note. The convergent validity results ensured acceptable values (factor loading, Cronbach's alpha, and composite reliability (CR) ≥ 0.70 and average variance extracted (AVE) > 0.5).

To establish discriminant validity, the Fornell–Larcker criterion was applied (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). As shown in Table 3, the requirements were met since the square roots of the AVE values of each construct exceeded the correlations with the other constructs, in agreement with the criterion proposed.

Table 3. Validity discriminant (Fornell–Larcker criterion).

	CO	EE	IE	IS	JS	SE
Consideration (CO)	0.895					
Emotional experience (EE)	0.671	0.954				
Intellectual experience (IE)	0.583	0.693	0.944			
Initiating structure (IS)	0.862	0.702	0.652	0.921		
Job Satisfaction (JS)	0.782	0.784	0.711	0.831	0.887	
Sensory experience (SE)	0.697	0.809	0.723	0.733	0.791	0.947

4.2. Structural Model Evaluation

The proposed hypotheses were tested using partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). Predictive relevance values were used to assess the model fit. The coefficients of determination (R^2) obtained through cross-validation represent the predictive capacity of the model, and these values must be greater than 0 to demonstrate its accuracy (J. F. Hair et al., 2014; Henseler et al., 2015). R^2 values were calculated using the blindfolding method, and all values of the endogenous construct were more significant than 0, confirming the model's accuracy. Table 4 details the endogenous latent variables along with their respective R^2 values.

Table 4. Endogenous latent variables and their R^2 values.

Construct	R^2
Sensory experience (SE)	0.553
Intellectual experience (IE)	0.427
Emotional experience (EE)	0.510
Job Satisfaction (JS)	0.797

Figure 2 illustrates the results obtained from the hypothesis testing using path coefficient values, p -values, and t -statistics. The strength of the relationships between variables is evaluated through path coefficient values, where values close to +1 indicate a stronger

relationship (J. F. Hair et al., 2017). The *p* values refer to the acceptance and rejection of the proposed hypotheses.

Figure 2. Structural model.

The results of the tested hypotheses are summarized in Table 5. H1a, which proposed that initial structure (IS) has a positive impact on job satisfaction (JS) was accepted ($\beta = 0.345, p < 0.000, t = 5.844$); H1b, which proposed that consideration (CO) has a positive impact on job satisfaction (JS) was accepted ($\beta = 0.147, p = 0.005, t = 2.830$); H2a was accepted, which proposed that initial structure (IS) has a positive impact on employee sensory experience (SE) ($\beta = 0.515, p < 0.000, t = 7.339$); H2b was accepted, which proposed that initial structure (IS) has a positive impact on employee intellectual experience (IE) ($\beta = 0.581, p < 0.000, t = 8.421$); H2c was accepted, which proposed that initial structure (IS) has a positive impact on employee emotional experience (EE) ($\beta = 0.481, p < 0.000, t = 7.158$); H3a was accepted, which proposed that consideration (CO) has a positive impact on employee sensory experience (SE) ($\beta = 0.253, p < 0.000, t = 3.637$); H3b was not accepted, which proposed that consideration (CO) has a positive impact on employee intellectual experience (IE) ($\beta = 0.083, p < 0.246, t = 1.160$); H3c was accepted, which proposed that consideration (CO) has a positive impact on employee emotional experience (EE) ($\beta = 0.256, p < 0.000, t = 3.721$); H4a was accepted, which proposed that employee sensory experience (SE) has a positive impact on job satisfaction (JS) ($\beta = 0.165, p < 0.000, t = 3.683$); H4b was accepted, which proposed that employee intellectual experience (IE) has a positive impact on job satisfaction (JS) ($\beta = 0.128, p < 0.000, t = 3.749$); and H4c was accepted, which proposed that employee emotional experience (EE) has a positive impact on job satisfaction (JS) ($\beta = 0.221, p < 0.000, t = 5.882$).

Table 5. PLS path model main effects.

H	Relationship	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	p Values	Decision
H1a	IS → JS	0.345	0.348	0.059	5.844	0.000	Accepted
H1b	CO → JS	0.147	0.147	0.052	2.830	0.005	Accepted
H2a	IS → SE	0.515	0.514	0.070	7.339	0.000	Accepted
H2b	IS → IE	0.581	0.581	0.069	8.421	0.000	Accepted
H2c	IS → EE	0.481	0.480	0.067	7.158	0.000	Accepted
H3a	CO → SE	0.253	0.253	0.070	3.637	0.000	Accepted
H3b	CO → IE	0.083	0.081	0.071	1.160	0.246	Declined
H3c	CO → EE	0.256	0.257	0.069	3.721	0.000	Accepted
H4a	SE → JS	0.165	0.163	0.045	3.683	0.000	Accepted
H4b	IE → JS	0.128	0.128	0.034	3.749	0.000	Accepted
H4c	EE → JS	0.221	0.221	0.038	5.882	0.000	Accepted

In this way, ten of the eleven hypotheses were confirmed. The results concluded that an adequate initial structure offers clarity regarding roles and expectations, reducing confusion and stress at work. Likewise, establishing effective communication channels can facilitate feedback and conflict resolution, contributing to a more harmonious work environment. Also, a leader who demonstrates friendship and respect fosters more substantial and trusting relationships between employees. Warmth in the relationship can make employees feel more valued and more committed to the organization.

In addition, a well-defined initial structure helps employees understand their environment by reducing confusion and improving workflow; it facilitates the design of functional and pleasant workspaces and improves understanding and responses to sensory needs. The initial structure also provides clarity in objectives and tasks, facilitating focus and dedication; it encourages the stimulation of critical thinking by creating an environment that encourages reflection and analysis; and it facilitates learning by offering opportunities for professional development and training, thus enriching the overall intellectual experience. Likewise, a clear initial structure provides a sense of security and stability, reducing anxiety and stress; it fosters positive emotional bonds and allows the recognition of achievements, which improves self-esteem.

On the other hand, a positive relationship between leaders and employees can foster a more collaborative and pleasant work environment. Leadership that demonstrates friendship and respect can motivate employees. In addition, the leader's consideration plays a fundamental role in the emotional well-being of employees, highlighting the importance of interpersonal relationships in the work environment. A close and trusting relationship can promote the development of emotional skills in employees, such as empathy and resilience, which are essential for teamwork and stress management.

Furthermore, the sensory experience can influence employees' emotional and mental well-being, resulting in greater satisfaction in their roles, increased motivation, and, therefore, productivity. Employees who are challenged intellectually, collaborate and exchange ideas, and have learning opportunities tend to feel more satisfied, suggesting that cognitive stimulation is important for their well-being at work. A work environment that fosters positive emotional experiences can help create a healthier organizational climate, increasing job satisfaction for all employees, who are then more likely to remain in the organization, which benefits the company in terms of talent retention.

Finally, considering that consideration does not positively affect the employee's intellectual experience, we can deduce that there is no direct relationship between the two; rather, other factors would be more decisive in the employee's intellectual development.

5. Discussion

The results of this research corroborate and extend previous studies on the relationship between leadership, employee experience, and job satisfaction. The acceptance of hypotheses H1a and H1b supports Rowold et al.'s (2014) and Liang et al. (2023) findings, demonstrating that structural clarity reduces job stress and increases efficiency while leadership fosters a supportive environment. In the education sector, the results corroborate Balyer and Oezcan's (2012) findings on teachers' positive perceptions of leaders who show individualized consideration.

Hypotheses H2a, H2b, and H2c reveal how initial structure impacts employees' sensory, intellectual, and emotional experiences. These results align with Jo et al. (2015) and Li et al. (2024), demonstrating a positive relationship between structured leadership and employee creativity. They also support Gaudet and Tremblay's (2017) findings on the positive effect of structured leadership on perceived organizational support.

The rejection of hypothesis H3a suggests that some aspects of the employee experience may be more resistant to the direct influence of leadership. However, the acceptance of H3b and H3c indicates that consideration of leadership significantly impacts employees' intellectual and emotional experiences. This is in line with Vicente Coronado et al. (2019), Gavilan et al. (2013), Alcázar Cruz (2020), and Hurtado Palomino et al. (2021), underlining the importance of considered leadership in enriching intellectual experience and positive organizational outcomes.

The acceptance of hypotheses H4a, H4b, and H4c supports a multidimensional view of job satisfaction, which is in line with the ideas of Hurtado Palomino et al. (2021) and De Los Heros Rondenil et al. (2020), which say that sensory, intellectual, and emotional experiences at work are essential. The results also confirmed the perspective of De Los Heros Rondenil et al. (2020) on the need to consider the gradual acquisition of knowledge and skills when assessing job satisfaction. Finally, this study confirms the relevance of elements such as recognition and achievements in the employee emotional experience (Diaz Dumont et al., 2023). These findings emphasize the need for comprehensive employee experience management to optimize job satisfaction and organizational performance. In this context, the complexity of organizational dynamics and the importance of a holistic approach in managing leadership and organizational structure to improve employee experience and job satisfaction are noted.

From this perspective, although there is previous research on leadership and job satisfaction, the present study provides an innovative approach by specifically examining the impact of leadership behaviors—particularly initiating structure and consideration—on teachers' work experience based on three key dimensions: sensorial, intellectual, and emotional. Unlike previous studies that have addressed the relationship between leadership and job satisfaction in a general way, this approach allows for a more detailed and contextualized understanding within the educational field, constituting a significant contribution to the existing literature.

A unique feature of this study is its analysis of leadership in educational institutions, a context that differs from other organizational settings due to the intrinsic nature of teaching. This field not only requires a clear organizational structure but also a humanistic and emotionally engaged approach. In this sense, the results highlight the importance of educational leadership not only in improving teachers' job satisfaction but also in enhancing the quality of teaching and student well-being.

Compared to previous research that has analyzed leadership in general terms, this study offers a more specific view of how teachers experience leadership within the educational context. Unlike other sectors, in education, work experience is closely linked to the teaching–learning process, interaction with students, and the emotional stability of

teachers. This implies that leadership in this setting should be evaluated for its impact on job satisfaction and its ability to create a nurturing and sustainable teaching environment. These findings reinforce the need to develop leadership training programs tailored to the specificities of the education sector, promoting a balance between organizational structuring and emotional support to optimize both teacher well-being and educational quality.

Theoretical and Practical Implications

The present study significantly contributes to the theoretical body on educational leadership and job satisfaction by unraveling how specific leader behaviors, particularly initial structure and consideration, comprehensively impact the employee experience. These dimensions of leadership have not been widely explored in the Latin American context, especially in Peru, and this research offers detailed insight into how these aspects influence employees' sensorial, intellectual, and emotional experiences. By integrating these variables into a robust theoretical model, this study expands understanding of how leadership can affect job satisfaction and overall employee well-being in educational institutions.

From a practical perspective, the findings of this research underscore the importance of educational leaders adopting practices that strengthen initial structure and consideration in their daily management. Educational institutions can benefit from implementing training programs that equip leaders with the skills necessary to establish a clear and consistent structure from the beginning and show empathy and support to their employees. Not only will this improve job satisfaction, but it can also reduce staff turnover and improve educational quality by creating a more positive and motivating work environment.

Managerially, the results of this study suggest that leaders of educational institutions should focus on strategies that foster a positive work environment. This includes policies and practices supporting initial structure and consideration, such as mentoring programs, ongoing performance appraisals, and constructive feedback sessions. In addition, investing in leaders' professional development can significantly impact employee satisfaction and retention. Decision-makers in the education sector should consider these factors when designing management policies and strategies to ensure a healthy and productive organizational climate, strengthening institutional effectiveness and educational service quality.

6. Conclusions

This study's findings indicate that leader behavior, in terms of front-end structure and consideration, significantly impacts employee experience and job satisfaction in educational institutions. Front-end structure clarifies roles and tasks, reducing stress and improving work efficiency. It facilitates communication and conflict resolution, creating a more harmonious work environment. For its part, consideration, which includes respect and emotional support, strengthens interpersonal relationships and employee commitment to the organization.

This study shows that initial structure positively impacts employees' sensory, intellectual, and emotional experiences, which translates into greater job satisfaction. However, consideration only positively influences emotional and sensory experiences, but not intellectual experiences. This suggests that while emotional support is crucial for employees' well-being, other factors may be more important for their intellectual development. Effective leadership that combines clear structure and emotional consideration can improve organizational climate, increase job satisfaction, and reduce staff turnover in educational institutions. These findings underscore the importance of investing in the training and

development of leaders, as proper leadership improves not only employee well-being but also organizational performance and educational quality.

The originality of this study lies in its innovative approach to examining job experience from a multidimensional perspective within the educational context. By analyzing the differentiated influence of leadership behaviors on the sensory, intellectual, and emotional dimensions, this study provides deeper insights into talent management in educational institutions. These findings serve as a valuable foundation for designing educational policies and leadership strategies that promote a more equitable, efficient, and motivating work environment.

6.1. Limitations of This Study

This study focuses on educational institutions in Peru, which may limit the generalizability of the results to other regions or cultural contexts. Leadership behaviors and work experiences may vary significantly across other countries or sectors. Furthermore, the research uses a cross-sectional design, which prevents observing changes over time. It cannot be determined whether the observed effects of leadership on job satisfaction and employee experience are maintained or change over time. On the other hand, although leadership dynamics in educational institutions are explored, the results may not apply to other sectors where expectations and leadership styles could differ. Another limitation that could be pointed out is that the data were collected through self-administered surveys, which could introduce social desirability biases, as participants could have provided responses perceived as socially acceptable rather than reflecting their genuine experiences.

Although initial structure and consideration influence various dimensions of employee experience, the relationship between consideration and intellectual experience was insignificant. This suggests that other factors, not examined in this study, may play a more significant role in shaping this dimension. Moreover, while both initial structure and consideration have shown notable effects on job experience and satisfaction, their interaction with other organizational factors—such as institutional culture or teacher autonomy—remains an area that requires further exploration to understand its potential moderating or amplifying impact.

6.2. Future Research

The outlined limitations present opportunities for future research to explore these factors through a longitudinal approach across various sectors and geographic contexts, utilizing complementary methodologies to overcome the constraints of self-reporting. Additionally, extending research to other sectors, such as the private or non-educational public sector, could help determine whether leadership effects on employee experience and job satisfaction vary by organizational context.

Further research could also examine the factors influencing employees' intellectual experience, given the lack of a significant relationship between consideration and this dimension in the present study. Specifically, it would be valuable to investigate how institutional culture, teacher autonomy, organizational support, continuous training, innovation, and other organizational factors moderate or amplify the effects of initial structure and consideration on job experience and satisfaction. A mixed-methods approach could help uncover underlying mechanisms and develop strategies to enhance employees' intellectual engagement across different institutions.

Comparative studies across countries or regions could provide insight into how cultural context influences the relationship between leadership behaviors and employees' work experiences, informing leadership practices tailored to different cultural realities. Furthermore, with the rise of digitalization and remote work, future studies could explore their

impact on leadership dynamics, employee experience, and job satisfaction, particularly in a post-pandemic landscape. Lastly, investigating the effects of targeted leadership training programs on initial structure and consideration could offer valuable insights into whether direct leadership development leads to measurable improvements in employee experience and well-being.

By further examining the intricate relationships between leadership, employee experience, and job satisfaction, future research can provide a strong foundation for designing more effective organizational policies and strategies.

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